

Labor Safety in Vinyl Acetate Production Workshops from Acetylene

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Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to provide principles and measures to ensure occupational safety during the production of vinyl acetate from acetylene. In order to provide effective and feasible principles and solutions, the author analyzed the characteristics of the materials to synthesize into vinyl acetate and the process of synthesizing vinyl acetate from acetylene.

Keywords: Vinyl acetate, acetylene, labor safety, Vietnam

1. Introduction

In daily life and production, there are many chemicals used. These chemicals, if careless, can cause skin burns, eye burns, even cancer and are a source of extremely dangerous fires. Therefore, adhering to the safety principles when working with chemicals is the way to protect yourself and those around you.

Working with chemicals whether directly or indirectly, it is difficult to avoid cases of chronic poisoning. That is, the poisoning will occur slowly, a little each day, but then at some point, the amount of toxin accumulated beyond the body's ability to eliminate itself, will cause disease that can lead to functional impairment. respiratory, liver function, inflammation and skin degeneration, even cancer ... and some flammable chemical products such as industrial alcohol, pharmaceutical alcohol, ...

Another case of intoxication will occur immediately as a result of being shot by a toxic substance in the skin, in the face, in the eyes or by the risks or accidents while working. In order to avoid unfortunate consequences, when working with all movements such as weighing, measuring, crushing, mixing, packing, experimenting, testing, etc. workers must not allow chemicals to be shot at people or clothing, care must be exercised and adherence strictly to certain principles.

Vinylization is an important process in the technology of synthesizing intermediates for the synthesis of final organic products. Vinyl acetate (VA) is one of the important monomers for making plastics and synthetic fibers. In addition, vinyl acetate is also used in the manufacture of high-strength adhesive paints, resistant to chemicals and oxidants.

The world's global petrochemical and gas processing industry is growing to meet the increasing needs of social life, the more methods of synthesis of vinylacetate are found and applied. Producing vinyl acetate mainly from the following raw materials:

- Take from acetylene and acetic acid
- Going from ethylene
- Going from some other material

(Ethylene production is most economical.)

In Vietnam, from abundant raw materials such as coal, oil, natural gas, ... the first refineries and gas processing plants are being built and developed. It will be an abundant source of raw materials for industry. The development of organic synthesis industry, including vinyl acetate manufacturing industry, so the research to produce high efficiency is the most important issue.

2. Literature review

2.1. Acetylen

Acetylene is a colorless gas, in pure form with a weak ether odor, condensing at -83.8°C (0.1102 MPa), critical temperature 35.5°C , critical pressure 6.04 MPa

- Specific gravity at 0°C and 760mmHg: 1,171 kg / m³
- Molecular weight: 26.02 Kg / Kmol
- Rate of heat: 0.402

When decomposition can occur explosive reactions, the temperature rises to 2800°C

Acetylene dissolves well in many organic and inorganic liquids. When burning acetylene emits a large amount of heat, the heat generating capacity of acetylene is 13,387 kcal / m³. Therefore, acetylene can be used to cut and weld metal

C₂H₂ has a molecular formula of CH ≡ CH, 3 bonds in the molecule including 1 σ and 2 π bonds. When participating in the chemical reaction, bond 3 is broken so double bonds and saturated compounds

a. Reaction like that.

- When acting with alkali metal Cu, Ag ... metal acetylene is very explosive

- When passing acetylene over metal Na heated at 150°C

Continue to cook 220°C

- - When acetylene passes through copper chloride solution in NH₃, it creates the ability of amorphous red brick color of copper acetylene.

b) Collective reaction.

- Acetylene combined with H₂ gives ethylene, paladin catalyst, p = 1 at, temperature $250-300^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The catalyst is Niken, the temperature

- - Acetylene acts with water when catalyst is Hg, H₂SO₄ to form acetate acetate.

75- 100⁰C

- When there is zinc oxide and iron oxide at 360-450^oC, acetylene acts with steam to form acetone

- Combined reaction with KOH-catalyzed vinyl alcohol, temperature is 150-160^oC, pressure is 4- 20at

- Effect with mercaptan, we get surplus vinyl O ete

- + clo → tetra clo etan :

- C₂H₂ + Hydro clorua → vinyl clorua :

This process is carried out in the gas phase there are HgCl₂, 150 ÷ 180^oC.

- with H₂SO₄ → vinyl sunfo :

- in 80^oC có CuCl₂, C₂H₂ + HCN → aerylonitril :

Acrylomitrol

- C₂H₂ + Halogen is too easy :

- Combined with halogen salt to create isomer compounds cis trans:

- Axetylen effect with organic acids has catalysis involved → este :

c. Polymerization

- In 200 ÷ 300°C There is copper powder, acetylene polymerization formed Kypren :

Used as an insulator.

- With HCl → vinyl acetylen.

- Coincidence in 600°C

2.2. AXIT AXETIC

Acetic acid is a colorless liquid with a strong odor; anhydrous acetic acid melts at 16.60C, boiling point 1180C, at a pressure of p = 101.3 kPa. Density 1.05 g / cm³.

Acetic acid (CH₃COOH) is insoluble in water, and is a good solvent for many inorganic and organic substances (dissolved P, S). It is a very stable compound, its vapor does not decompose at 4000C, the heating temperature is 3490 kcal / mol.

CH₃COOH is widely applied in food industry, textile and in organic synthesis.

Acetic acid has the ability to participate in chemical reactions so it is widely used:

- Effects on metals:

- Esterification reaction:

-

CH₃COOH There are many important reactions in organic synthesis to form these monome : axetat xenlulo, vinyl axetat...

2.3. vinyl axetat

Vinyl acetate has the formula $\text{CH}_2 = \text{CHCOOCH}_3$, abbreviated as VA, $M = 86.09$. Odorless, flammable liquid. Slightly soluble in water (2- 2.4% mass fraction). Good soluble in ethyl alcohol and diethyl ether. At room temperature vinyl acetate is less stable and is more prone to polymerization to form polyethyl acetate

Some of the physical properties of VA are given in the following table:

Melting point	72,8	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Melting temperature	-93,2	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Density at 200C	0,932	g/ml
Viscosity at 200C	0,43	mPa.S
Ignition temperature	-8	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Burning temperature	385	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Fire limit	23 ÷ 13,4	% thể tích
Specific heat	926	kJ/kg
Heat to vaporize at 72.10C	79,3	kJ/kg
Heat of fire	82,0	kJ/mol
Thermal polymerization reaction	1035,8	kJ/kg
Solubility of H ₂ O in VA at 200C	0,9	% khối lượng
The solubility of VA in H ₂ O at 200C	2,3	% khối lượng

In vinyl acetate molecule, $\text{CH}_3\text{COOCH} = \text{CH}_2$ has double bonds so it has full chemical properties of unsaturated compound.

- Participate in hydrolysis reaction:

As an ester, it is hydrolysed in H^+ medium. The acidic vinyl acetate hydrolyzate joins us with polyvinyl alcohol and polyvinyl acetate.

Depending on the degree of hydrolysis of the product, it can be made of artificial leather or hydrolyzed completely, we can use polymeric vinylic as vinylon fiber.

- When copolymer vinyl acetate with vinyl chloride, we get vinylic resin used to make thin films, paints, impregnated materials, etc.

- VA intra-molecular metabolism

-Join the combined reaction with:

+ Halogen

+ HX (X: halogen)

+ Acetic acid

+ Hydro cyanide

+ Hydro peroxide

+ Ankađien

Methods to produce vinyl acetate.

There are the following methods:

- From acetic acid and acetylene. (in liquid and gas phase).

- From diaxetyl ether and acetaldehyde

- From ethylene and acetic acid and O₂

- From methyl acetate or dimethyl ether with CO and H₂ in the aqueous phase in the presence of homogeneous catalysts such as Rh salt or precious metals such as Pt give us ethylene diaxetate and hydrolyze to give vinyl acetate and CH₃COOH.

3. Vinyl acetate synthesis process.

3.1. General concept.

VA synthesis reaction from C₂H₂ and CH₃COOH with the catalyst is the salt of transition metals (Hg, Zn, Cd, ...) on the activated carbon carrier, conducted in the gas phase. The reaction that produces the product is an important monome reaction that occurs as follows:

The reaction was conducted at a temperature of 170 - 2200C, the reaction was conducted at atmospheric pressure in a beam-shaped device and cooled by water. The generated steam is used to encapsulate the reaction temperature due to the large exothermic reaction, so it needs good thermal separation to ensure the process, avoiding the creation of byproducts and catalytic decomposition. VA product efficiency is very high from 95 - 99% calculated on the conversion of CH₃COOH and 92 - 95% calculated according to C₂H₂.

The advantage of this process is overcoming the disadvantages of synthetic vinyl acetate in the liquid phase such as:

- Resistant to equipment corrosion
- Create fewer by-products
- High response performance

In the process of synthesizing vinyl acetate from C_2H_2 and CH_3COOH , there are byproducts ethyl diaacetate, acetone, ...

Therefore we need to mention the factors that influence the process in order to limit the mistakes made in the process

Effect of catalysis.

Through many researches on private catalysts, zinc acetate and cadmium acetate on activated carbon are two effective catalysts and widely applied in the VA synthesis industry.

Here we use zinc acetate / activated carbon with a content of 3% of the amount prepared by dry method impregnating the amount of zinc acetate / activated carbon as the catalyst used for one liter of acetylene (C_2H_2). It also affects the catalytic activity and metabolism of acetic acid. The relationship is shown in the figure: From the graph we see an increase of 10 - 30 grams of catalyst per liter of C_2H_2 in 1 hour of the conversion efficiency of acetic acid. But if the amount of catalyst is less than 10 grams, the conversion efficiency is reduced, the causes of the catalytic activity are acetylene and VA polymerization forming polymers covering the catalytic surface, or when the reaction is radiative. a lot of heat causes local heating causing the catalyst to decompose unclean acetylene with catalytic toxins.

Therefore, we must control the temperature and clean the material well

The effect of temperature.

Reaction temperature also significantly affects the metabolism of acetic acid. The suitable temperature for zinc acetate catalyst is 180 - 2300 C.

The biggest VA efficiency is when the process temperature is less than 1800C, the VA efficiency will be very small, and if the process temperature is greater than 2300C, the VA's performance will decrease.

4. Labor safety in the production works Vinyl acetate

Safety rules when working with chemicals

Chemicals in different industries are different toxic. Working with these chemicals has great safety risks that need attention to avoid unfortunate events. Therefore, workers need to master the principles of occupational safety when working with chemicals, especially toxic flammable chemicals on the state list.

The following are basic but important rules for working with chemicals:

▶ Always wear protective gear and inspect them carefully to ensure safety before use. Replace broken, torn protective gear because they will not meet the protection.

▶ Follow all procedures that have been issued and perform the job duties as trained.

▶ Learn about emergency procedures and equipment. Understanding emergency procedures means knowing how to evacuate, knowing how to report emergencies and how to deal with fires and leaks, as well as how to give first aid when a colleague is injured in problem.

▶ Be careful and plan ahead. Think about possible bad situations and pay attention to what you are doing in the process.

▶ Store all materials appropriately, separate easily combustible materials, and store them in a cool, dry, well-ventilated area.

▶ Read the label and material safety data sheet (MSDS) before using any material to make sure you are aware of the risks and precautions.

► Make sure all containers are labeled and chemicals are in proper containers. Do not use any chemicals that are not contained or labeled appropriately. Report damaged containers immediately or unreadable on labels.

► Keep your body and workplace clean. After contact with any chemicals, wash with soap and water. Clean the work surface at least once during the shift to minimize the risk of contamination.

► Only use the material for its intended purpose only. For example, use solvents to wash your hands or gasoline to clean the device.

► Do not eat or drink while working with chemicals and if your hands are exposed to chemicals, do not use cosmetics or contact lenses.

In any activity, human life must always be guaranteed. Therefore, in the production process, the life and health of workers must be ensured with the slogan:

“Production must be safe

Safe to produce”

In VA factory, first of all, you need to know the toxic, flammable and explosive nature of chemicals. Therefore, it is necessary to put forth work to ensure labor safety.

4.1. Work safety assurance

The work of ideological education.

Labor protection is public so the work is largely done by the workers themselves. The production manager and executive must regularly educate workers to comply with the factory's set rules on labor protection, and regularly check the implementation of regulations and safety. When operating operations, promptly solve when incidents occur.

There is fostering for night shift workers and toxic workers.

Labor protection equipment.

In the factory, especially in the VA production workshop, the full allocation of labor protection equipment such as pants, shirts, shoes, hats, gloves, masks is extremely necessary. These are factors intended to prevent occupational accidents and diseases. At the same time, remind and regularly check the implementation of workers in this regard.

Technical measures.

Technical measures are the most important namely:

- Strictly perform the routine maintenance of machinery.
- Fully equipped with production tools in accordance with technical standards.
- Electric equipment and devices must be properly shielded to ensure safety.
- The motion system like a motor must cover sure.
- Checking raw materials before putting them into production.
- Equipping and regular maintenance of valves, dynamic parts.
- Regularly inspect material pipes and products.
- Absolutely follow the technology requirements.

- Use flammable chemicals, causing burns must be absolutely careful.

4.2. Labor hygiene

It is necessary to do good labor hygiene to avoid occupational diseases. In the production process, there must be ventilation and lighting systems for the workshops.

Ventilation system.

During the operation of the machine, there is a process of heating, generating heat, there are toxic gases so there must be ventilation measures for each stage. In addition to natural ventilation, it is necessary to arrange an air intake system (type fan of 4000m³ / h).

Lighting systems.

It is necessary to ensure the natural and artificial light elements to create conditions for workers to be comfortable and highly productive, accurately and avoid occupational diseases. Working night shifts should ensure light for workshops.

Personal hygiene system.

The workshop has a toilet area on each floor, including: changing rooms, washing, bathing, hygiene to ensure the health of workers during production.

Consumption of water for workshop workers takes an average of 8 m³ / person per month. An annual consumption of $8 \times 12 = 96$ m³ / person / year.

* Comment.

In order to improve labor productivity and bring about high economic efficiency for society, it is necessary to take care of the life, health and needs of workers. Comfortable working conditions, guaranteed health will help people energetically produce labor.

5. Conclusion

Researching to find a valuable product for social life is a great achievement of applied scientists and putting into production these valuable products of great importance, it requires People who study design must have a role and a great responsibility for the work.

With the scientist Klatt synthesizing V.A has made a big change in materials for the 20th century. Vinyl acetate vinyl has many advantages compared to similar products. V.A output is constantly increasing every year. Scientists are always finding new catalyst systems for the synthesis of V.A, along with that is innovation in technology.

To put an outcome from research into production is a complex process that requires precision and meticulousness, the designer must understand all the issues related to the manufacturing process. In theory, it is necessary to understand clearly the physical and chemical properties of raw materials and products. At the same time, catalytic, kinetic and mechanism issues are important factors to improve the quality and productivity of the process. Based on the theoretical basis combined with design topics, it is possible to choose appropriate equipment and technology to take into account. Not all lines put into application also achieve the desired results, in addition to the known advantages in theory, in reality, there are still many problems arising. Therefore, the designer must continue to put into practice to promote advantages and overcome disadvantages in order to improve productivity and product quality. The design of this project is still theoretical, compared with the fact that there are still many defects, but it has helped technology students know the basic steps in the design process.

Currently, there are many new VA production technologies and technologies from different sources of raw materials, in which the VA synthesis method from ethylene and acetic acid is considered to be an economically effective method. Best. The ethylene source after the petrochemical refinery in our country started operating is very suitable for this development trend. Therefore, building a VA factory from ethylene is essential for the country's economy.

References

- i. *Chemical process and technology handbook, volumes 1, 2, Department of process equipment and chemical technology, Hanoi University of Science and Technology.*
- ii. *Basic organic synthesis, volume 1,2, Hanoi University of Science and Technology 1986.*
- iii. *Phan Minh Tan, Petrochemical organic synthesis, Volume 1, Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology, 1994.*
- iv. *Plastics manufacturing technique, volume 1, Hanoi University of Science and Technology.*
- v. *Organic chemistry and synthesis, Hanoi University of Science and Technology, 1974.*
- vi. *Handbook summarizing chemical engineers, Vuong Dinh Nhan, 1961.*
- vii. *Compound reaction equipment of organic compounds, Tran Cong Khanh, Hanoi University of Science and Technology, 1986.*
- viii. *Organic chemistry, volume 2, Hoang Trong Yem, Nguyen Dang Quang, 1996.*
- ix. *Encyclopedice of chemical Technology, Vol 5, 8, 14, 15, 21.*
- x. *Ulmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial chemistry, Vol A1, A5, A9, A22, A27.*
- xi. *Petro chemical processes, Vol A2 Alain Chauvel, Gilles Lefe brre.*
- xii. *Calculation of equipment processes in the chemical and food industry, volume 2, Nguyen Bin, Science and Technology Publishing House 2001.*